

Practical Free-form RTI Acquisition with Local Spot Lights

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Problem statement

- **Multi-light reflectance techniques**
 - Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI)
 - Photometric Stereo (PS)
- **Appearance and geometry measurements**
 - Study the interaction between light, geometry and material
- **Huge amount of literature**
 - Calibrated setups
 - Unknown lighting
 - Unknown reflectance
 - Unknown lighting AND reflectance
 - Multiview or more wild out-of-the-lab setups

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Problem statement

- **Used in many practical applications**
 - Cultural Heritage, Medical investigation, Underwater 3D data acquisition, ... many more!
- **Light calibration**
 - Fixed light domes, free-form acquisition, hybrid setups
- **Classic light assumptions**
 - Far point light → collimated, uniform
 - Local point light → non-collimated, uniform, distance fall-off
 - Do not hold for common illuminants (e.g., LED lights)
- **Local spot light calibration → non-collimated, non-uniform**

Related work

- **Light direction and intensity calibration**
- **2D image domain**
 - [GDR*15] [CPM*16]
 - Light direction
 - Reflective spheres
 - 2D linear interpolation
 - Light intensity
 - White planar target
 - 2D quadratic interpolation
 - [SSSF13] [AP14]
 - Flat reference object with known albedo
 - Per-pixel light calibration & correction

[GDR*15] GIACHETTI A., DAFFARA C., REGHELIN C., GOBBETTI E., PINTUS R.: Light calibration and quality assessment methods for reflectance transformation imaging applied to artworks' analysis. In SPIE Optical Metrology (2015), International Society for Optics and Photonics, pp. 95270B–95270B.

[CPM*16] CIORTAN I., PINTUS R., MARCHIORO G., DAFFARA C., GIACHETTI A., GOBBETTI E.: A practical reflectance transformation imaging pipeline for surface characterization in cultural heritage. In The 14th Eurographics Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage (October 2016). To appear.

[SSSF13] SUN J., SMITH M., SMITH L., FAROOQ A.: Sampling light field for photometric stereo. International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering 5, 1 (2013), 14.

[AP14] ANGELOPOULOU M. E., PETROU M.: Uncalibrated flatfielding and illumination vector estimation for photometric stereo face reconstruction. Machine vision and applications 25, 5 (2014), 1317–1332.

Related work

- **Issues**

- No knowledge about 3D positions of calibration targets
- Assumptions on direction/intensity behavior across 2D image domain (linear, quadratic)
- No 3D light model → neglect effects due to variation in depth (z-axis)
- Valid only for planar objects

[GDR*15] GIACHETTI A., DAFFARA C., REGHELIN C., GOBBETTI E., PINTUS R.: Light calibration and quality assessment methods for reflectance transformation imaging applied to artworks' analysis. In SPIE Optical Metrology (2015), International Society for Optics and Photonics, pp. 95270B–95270B.

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Related work

- **3D light calibration**
- **[HWBC15]**
 - Calibrate near-light positions
 - Fall-off due to distance and camera vignetting
 - Point light model → uniform intensity

[HWBC15] HUANG X., WALTON M., BEARMAN G., COSSAIRT O.: Near light correction for image relighting and 3d shape recovery. In 2015 Digital Heritage (2015), vol. 1, IEEE, pp. 215–222.

Related work

- **3D light calibration**
- **[HWBC15]**
 - Calibrate near-light positions
 - Fall-off due to distance and camera vignetting
 - Point light model → uniform intensity
- **[XSJ*15]**
 - LED-based photometric stereo
 - Light position + principal axis
 - Known fixed LED parameters
 - Strong constraint:
 - Optical axis collinear with light direction at a specular point

[HWBC15] HUANG X., WALTON M., BEARMAN G., COSSAIRT O.: Near light correction for image relighting and 3d shape recovery. In 2015 Digital Heritage (2015), vol. 1, IEEE, pp. 215–222.

[XSJ*15] XIE L., SONG Z., JIAO G., HUANG X., JIA K.: A practical means for calibrating an led-based photometric stereo system. Optics and Lasers in Engineering 64 (2015), 42–50.

Our approach

- **3D light calibration scenario:**
 - Light model based on cosine-power term
 - Wide range of light sources: ideal point lights, Lambertian emitters, spot light illuminators...
 - Light positions → calibrated perspective camera + reflective spheres
 - Unknown per-image principal-axis
 - Unknown light parameters (intensity and fall-off)
 - Calibration target → white Lambertian plane
- **Our contribution:**
 - Numerical optimization framework → per-image principal-axis + light parameters
 - Early evaluation → analytical and real-world

Input & Pre-processing

- **Input data**

- Set of images → same viewpoint + different illuminations
- Camera intrinsic parameters
- Image mask (pixels on white Lambertian planar target)

- **Pre-processing**

- Image undistortion
- Light positions
- Plane equation of the planar target

Lighting model

$$I(i, w) = \frac{\rho(w)}{d^2(i, w)} L(i, w) [\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{n}(w)]$$

- **Near-field Lambertian equation**
- **At each point P in the target corresponds a pixel w in all acquired images (fixed viewpoint)**
- $\rho(w)$ - **albedo of point P**
- $\hat{n}(w)$ - **normal of point P**
- $\hat{l}(i, w)$ - **direction of the light at point P - $\hat{l}(i, w)$**
- $L(i, w)$ - **intensity of the light at point P**
- $d(i, w)$ - **light to point P distance**
- $I(i, w)$ - **Irradiance at pixel w of image i**

$$L(i, w) = L_0 [\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{a}(i)]^m$$

- **Cosine-power term**
- L_0 - **maximum emitted intensity**
- $\hat{a}(i)$ - **direction of the principal axis**
- m - **exponential fall-off**

Image mask

$$w = (u, v) \in W$$

Lighting model

$$I(i, w) = \frac{\rho(w)}{d^2(i, w)} L_0 [\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{a}(i)]^m [\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{n}(w)]$$

Known variables

- $I(i, w)$ - **Irradiance at pixel w of image i**
- $\rho(w) = 1$ - **albedo of the whole target**
- $d(i, w)$ - **light to point P distance** - $d(i, w) = \|P_L(i) - P(w)\|$
- $\hat{l}(i, w)$ - **direction of the light at point P** - $\hat{l}(i, w) = [P_L(i) - P(w)] / \|P_L(i) - P(w)\|$
- $\hat{n}(w)$ - **normal of point P**

Unknown variables

- L_0 - **maximum emitted intensity**
- $\hat{a}(i)$ - **direction of the principal axis**
- m - **exponential fall-off**

Spot light calibration

- **Given N input images we have $N + 2$ unknown variables**
 - L_0 , m , and $\hat{a}(i)$ for $i = 1 \dots N$
- **Non-linear minimization strategy**

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{L_0, m, \hat{a}(i)} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{w \in W} \|\tilde{L}(i, w) - L(i, w)\|^2$$

$$\tilde{L}(i, w) = \frac{I(i, w) d^2(i, w)}{\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{n}(w)}$$

$$L(i, w) = L_0 [\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{a}(i)]^m$$

- **We need initial guess for L_0 , m , and $\hat{a}(i)$**

Initial guess – N Principal axes

- Per-image computation (we omit i here)
 1. Selection of a subset S of image pixels
 2. Find the set of points in the plane $P(s)$ for $s \in S$
 3. Define a set of candidate axes $\hat{a}(s) = (P_L - P(s)) / \|P_L - P(s)\|$
 4. Compute the set of pairs $\{L_0(\hat{a}(s)), m(\hat{a}(s))\}$ by logarithmic least-squares fitting (closed-form)

$$L(w) = L_0(\hat{a}(s)) [\hat{l}(w) \cdot \hat{a}(s)]^{m(\hat{a}(s))}$$

$$\downarrow$$

$$\ln(L(w)) = \ln(L_0(\hat{a}(s))) + m(\hat{a}(s)) \ln [\hat{l}(w) \cdot \hat{a}(s)]$$

$$\downarrow$$

$$y = A + B \ln(x)$$

5. We take the axis with the minimum residual

$$R = \sum_{w \in W} \|A + B \ln(x_w) - y_w\|^2$$

Initial guess – L_0, m

- **Starting point**
 - Initial N guesses $\hat{a}(i)$ for $i = 1 \dots N$
 - The corresponding N pairs $\{L_0(\hat{a}(i)), m(\hat{a}(i))\}$
 - The corresponding N residuals $R(i)$
- **Select the best pair $\{L_0(\hat{a}(i)), m(\hat{a}(i))\}$**
 - 1. Order pairs by increasing residual**
 - 2. Discard the top 50% (remove outliers)**
 - 3. Choose the one that minimizes**

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{w \in W} \|A + B \ln(x_w) - y_w\|^2$$

Global solution

- **Starting point**

- Initial N guesses $\hat{a}(i)$ for $i = 1 \dots N$
- Initial L_0, m
- Measurements $\tilde{L}(i, w) = \frac{I(i, w)d^2(i, w)}{\hat{l}(i, w) \cdot \hat{n}(w)}$ for $i = 1 \dots N$ and $w \in W$

- **Local non-linear minimization**

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{L_0, m, \hat{a}(i)} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{w \in W} \left\| \ln[\tilde{L}(i, w)] - \ln[L(i, w)] \right\|^2$$

Results - Synthetic diffuse plane

Light Constellation
53 Positions

Image mask

- **LED light with emitting angle $\theta = 15^\circ \rightarrow m \approx 20$**
- **LED light intensity $L_0 \approx 500K$**

Results - Synthetic diffuse plane

Re-rendering error

Original

Point light model

Spot light model

Results - Synthetic diffuse plane

Re-rendering error

Min

Max

Med

Std

Method	Min	Max	Average	Median	Std
Point light	0.0	0.24	0.07	0.07	0.05
Spot light	0.0	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.01

Results - Synthetic diffuse plane Compensated images

Original

Point light

[GDR*15]

Spot light

Results - Synthetic diffuse plane Normals

Method	Min	Max	Average	Median	Std
Point light	0.03	5.3	2.6	2.7	1.3
[GDR* 15]	0.04	13.1	6.3	6.1	2.9
Spot light	0.03	3.1	1.6	1.6	0.6

RTI/PS vs Micro-profilometer

Bronzital 10c

Copper 10c

Quadrans

Original

No Calib

[GDR*15]

Point light

Spot light

RTI/PS vs Micro-profilometer

	Non-calib.	[GDR*15]	Point	Spot
Bronzital 10c	15.08	5.95	7.39	4,93
Copper 10c	20,62	11,41	12.29	8.06
Quadrans	13.84	6.82	8.38	6.68

Conclusions

- **Practical spot lights calibration framework for RTI/PS**
- **Advantages**
 - Straightforward to implement
 - No parameters → easy to use by non-experts (e.g., CH)
 - Compliant with common illuminants (e.g., LEDs)
 - Near-light → small setups (or big objects???)
 - Integration into existing systems (e.g., fixed domes)
- **Drawbacks**
 - Presence of calibration targets (e.g., white Lambertian plane)
 - Requires light positions (e.g., reflective spheres)
 - Not out-of-the-lab/wild setups (e.g., internet collections)...typical collimated
- **Just an early experiment → future work:**
 - Improve initial estimation / numerical method
 - More extensive validation
 - Apply a PS algorithm with depth (non-planar objects)

Thank you!

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